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Towards the SDG Challenges

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T4-P-30 Volatiles other than ethanol in unrecorded and recorded fruit spirits – health risk assessment

Branislava Srđenović Čonić^{86/87*}, Ljilja Torović⁸⁶, Nebojša Kladar^{86/87}, Biljana Božin^{86/87}, Nebojša Salaj⁸⁶, Kusonić Dejan⁸⁶, Jan Sudić^{86/88}

KEYWORDS: Volatiles, spirits, HHS-GC-FID, margin of exposure

INTRODUCTION:

Per capita alcohol consumption in the WHO European Region is the highest in the world, which results in proportionally higher levels of burden of disease attributable to alcohol use compared to other regions. Mortality attributed to alcohol consumption remains a problem in countries located at Southeast Europe and consumption of unrecorded homemade spirits is stated to be one of the leading causes. Some alcoholic beverages contain volatile components; other than ethanol. Methanol has been described to be the most common cause for surrogate toxicity, while acetaldehyde may contribute to the carcinogenicity and higher alcohols have also been speculated as a cause for unrecorded alcohol toxicity (liver cirrhosis) in Eastern Europe. They are not subject to safety control, thus raising the question about health risks related to the presence of carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic volatiles.

OBJECTIVES:

Out of 153 fruit spirit samples collected during 2020 in Vojvodina (Serbia), 26 with tax stamp were marked as recorded, whereas 127 produced in private homes or small-scale distilleries and obtained mainly directly from the producers were marked as unrecorded. All samples were analyzed by HSS-GC-FID for the presence of acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate, methanol and higher alcohols (n-propanol, n-butanol, isobutanol, isoamyl alcohol, n-amyl alcohol) and resulting concentrations were compared with toxicological thresholds proposed by the Alcohol Measures for Public Health Research Alliance project (AMPHORA). The margin of exposure approach was used to assess the health risk of unrecorded and recorded spirits.

METHOD / DESIGN:

The margin of exposure approach (MOE-ratio of toxicological threshold values and estimated daily exposure) was used for the risk assessment, where NOAEL (no observed adverse effect level) was used as the toxicological threshold value, except for methanol where lower one-sided confidence limit of benchmark dose (BMDL) was used. Estimated daily exposure for each substance of interest (mg/kg bw/day) was calculated by multiplying measured concentration of substance (mg/L of pure alcohol) and daily alcohol consumption (L of pure alcohol per day) divided with body weight (kg).

For the daily alcohol consumption in Serbia four scenarios were employed – average consumption on the population level, regular drinkers only, chronic heavy drinkers version A (share of recorded and unrecorded alcohol consumption) and chronic heavy drinkers version B (exclusive consumption of recorded or unrecorded spirits)

RESULTS:

For the unrecorded spirits, AMFORA limit was exceeded for acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate, methanol and higher alcohols in

⁸⁶ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia.

Corresponding author: BRANISLAVA.SRDJENOVIC-CONIC@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁸⁷ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Center for Medical and Pharmaceutical Investigations and Quality Control, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

⁸⁸ Institute of Occupational Health Novi Sad, Futoska 121, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

5%, 66%, 21% and 1% of the samples, respectively, while for the recorded spirits limits were exceeded only in case of ethyl acetate (4% of the samples) and higher alcohols (1%). Statistically significant differences in content of volatiles between unrecorded and recorded spirits were noticed in case of ethyl acetate, isobutanol and n-amyl alcohol.

The MOE values for acetaldehyde dropped below 1000 even at average consumption level for 31% of unrecorded and 35% of recorded spirit samples for both sexes, rising up to 98% for both men and women considering consumption of solely unrecorded or 88% in case of exclusive consumption of recorded spirits. Similar situation was noticed for methanol where in average consumption scenario MOE values dropped below 100 in 73% of unrecorded and 58% of recorded samples, rising up to 85% for recorded and even 97% for unrecorded spirits in chronic heavy drinkers scenario B. Higher alcohols exerted health risk only in chronic heavy drinkers scenario version B (around 70% for both types of spirits), while only 4% of recorded spirits posed a risk in heavy drinkers scenario version A.

CONCLUSIONS:

The obtained results suggest that, although slightly higher content of some volatiles was observed in unrecorded spirits, there was no substantial difference in consequent health risk. Control measures should be included in order to maintain the quality of both recorded and unrecorded spirits and minimize the potential adverse health effects.

T4-P-31 Antihyperglycemic potential of hemp extracts (*Cannabis Sativa*, Cannabaceae)

Nebojša Kladar*, Marija Perić, Katarina Bijelić, Blagoje Prpa, Dejan Kusonić, Biljana Božin, Branislava Srđenović Čonić⁸⁹

KEYWORDS: Hemp; *Cannabis sativa*; α -amylase; α -glucosidase; antioxidant potential

INTRODUCTION:

Cannabis sativa L., Cannabaceae is the only representative of *Cannabis L.* genus. The exploitation of *C. sativa* by mankind has a long history. It is important to highlight the classification of *Cannabis* species based on their primary purpose of utilization. Namely, the species containing more than 0.2, or 0.3% (depending on national regulations) of Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (Δ^9 -THC) are considered psychoactive and are in most of the countries illegal to possess and use. On the other hand, species containing lower amounts of Δ^9 -THC and higher amounts of cannabidiol (CBD) are legal for cultivation and are better known as industrial hemp, or simply hemp. They show demonstrated history of usage for production of fiber, as well as different food products, because of the exceptional nutritional value of hemp fruits, commonly marked as "seeds". Besides the previously mentioned terpenophenolic compounds, *Cannabis* species contain other classes of secondary metabolites which have the potential to exhibit beneficial biological effects.

OBJECTIVES:

The aim of the conducted study was to evaluate the antihyperglycemic and antioxidant potential of water and ethanolic hemp extracts, followed by preliminary and detailed chemical characterization of the obtained extracts.

METHOD / DESIGN:

The plant material included five samples of commercially available hemp teas which were further extracted in a form of infusion and ethanolic macerate (70% v/v, 24h). The solvents were evaporated and dry extract yield was quantified. The

⁸⁹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Serbia.

*Corresponding author: nebojsa.kladar@mf.uns.ac.rs